

Emergent spatial patterns can indicate upcoming regime shifts in a realistic model of coral community - Supplement 2: Null models for indicator trends

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In our work, we investigated indicator trends along gradients of stress. Changes in indicator values can arise because of changes in spatial structure, e.g. how clustered coral cells tend to be in a landscape, but also because of changes in covers. The average patch size for example will most often be lower in a landscape with low coral cover than high coral cover. In addition, the covers of each state are not independent, and, for instance, the clustering of coral cells in space can increase simply as the result of being restricted to bare areas left by algae.

To consider informative trends in indicators, it is thus necessary to remove both the effect of (i) changes in covers and (ii) non-independence of the covers of each state in the landscape. To do so we compared indicator values computed on the observed landscapes, with the same indicators computed on randomized matrices. For example, for indicators based on coral cover, we computed the indicator value (spatial variance, autocorrelation or mean patch size) on the landscape resulting from the model simulation, but with the coral and bare cells shuffled, and algal cells left at the same spatial positions. This allows constructing a null expected indicator value that reflects the fact that coral can establish anywhere there is a bare area in a landscape with equal probability, but not where algae are already present. Following the same reasoning, for indicators based on algal cover, we randomized the algae and bare cells (and left coral cells at their original position). We shuffled the matrix 128 times to compute an average null indicator value (spatial variance, autocorrelation or patch size).

We obtain from the above process one observed indicator value (y_{obs}), and one average null value (μ_{null}). The difference, or relative difference may be then used to investigate how indicator trends change along a gradient, after taking into account the effect of changing, non-independent covers. For the moran's I indicator we used the difference between the observed and null value ($y_{obs} - \mu_{null}$). To check that this difference was able to remove the effect of changing covers, we created synthetic matrices with similar autocorrelation, but different proportion of corals and bare areas (and no algae). We confirmed that the difference $y_{obs} - \mu_{null}$ showed no relationship on average with the cover of corals (Figure S2.1).

Figure S2.1. Difference $y_{obs} - \mu_{null}$ for the Moran's I for matrices of constant autocorrelation, but changing coral covers. Each point is the difference $y_{obs} - \mu_{null}$ computed on a synthetic matrix, and the blue line indicates the trend (LOESS fit) along changes in coral cover. A flat line indicates no dependence of the difference with coral cover.

For the variance indicator, we used the relative difference $(y_{obs} - \mu_{null})/\mu_{null}$ so that the difference would not depend on the cover of coral. We did so because the absolute difference $y_{obs} - \mu_{null}$ appeared to depend on cover (Figure S2.2).

Figure S2.2: Difference (a) $y_{obs} - \mu_{null}$ and relative difference (b) $(y_{obs} - \mu_{null}) / \mu_{null}$ for the variance indicator for matrices of constant autocorrelation, but changing coral covers. Each point is the difference (a) or relative difference (b) computed on a synthetic matrix, and the blue line indicates the trend (LOESS fit) along changes in coral cover.

Carrying the same work with the average patch size shows that the raw difference $y_{obs} - \mu_{null}$ remains sensitive to the cover of a state in the landscape (Figure S2.3). Going from 100% to ~70% cover will make the difference increase, then this difference will slightly decrease going from 70% cover to zero. This means that as the cover of a given state changes along a gradient of stress, the difference in average patch size will change as well, even in the absence of changes in spatial structure. Taking the relative change $(y_{obs} - \mu_{null}) / \mu_{null}$ is not able to correct for this problem (not shown here). For practical purposes, in this work we used the raw difference despite these flaws, as in practice we observed different trends despite similar changes in coral covers. For example, in the “increasing coral mortality” scenario (increasing m_c), comparing $d_0=0$ and $d_0=-0.5$, both coral covers goes from ~100% to ~75% before the shift, but in the latter case there is a clear negative trend, while no trend is observed in the former. Despite this non-independence, changes in $y_{obs} - \mu_{null}$ for the average patch still showed informative trends.

Figure S2.3: Difference $y_{obs} - \mu_{null}$ between the average patch size and the expected null patch size. Each point is the difference $y_{obs} - \mu_{null}$ computed on a matrix with constant autocorrelation, and the blue line indicates the trend (LOESS fit) along changes in coral cover.

This non-independence arises in part from the fact that patch size distributions are typically very skewed, often resembling power-laws or log-normal distributions (Kéfi et al. 2007; Pueyo 2011; Sankaran et al. 2019). This makes the estimation of statistics such as the mean sometimes unstable and subject to finite-size effects. For example, a patch size distribution that would follow a pure power-law may have an undefined mean, which means in practice the mean patch size over a set of replicate simulations will be extremely variable. Other descriptors may help alleviate this issue (e.g. based on fitting the observed patch size distribution to various candidate distributions), but come with their own statistical challenges (much discussed in the context of arid ecosystems; (Kéfi et al. 2010; Pueyo 2011; Meloni et al. 2017)). For practical purposes, we used the mean patch size here for its simplicity, and despite these issues, as it was able to capture informative trends. However, applications of this work to empirical data could require revising this choice, or consider its drawbacks carefully.

References

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